

Original Article

Sex differences in the association between physical functioning and cognition in two Central European Populations

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PFS and cognition function_EJN_final_revised.docx	Main Document - MS Word	197.7 KB	Page 4
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Sex differences in the association between physical functioning and cognition in two Central European Populations

Short title: Women, Physical Function, and Cognition

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1 **Abstract**

2 **Background:** Evidence on the relationship between physical and cognitive functions remains inconsistent,
3 and the role of sex differences is underexplored. This study examines the predictive value of a composite
4 Physical Functioning Score (PFS) for cognitive function and assesses sex-specific associations in an Eastern
5 European population.

6 **Methods:** Data from 7,309 participants (mean age 59 ± 7.3 years) from the Czech Republic and Poland
7 arms of HAPIEE study were analyzed. PFS was derived from a 23-item measure including activity of daily
8 living (ADL/IADL), grip strength, functional limitations, and physical activity. Cognitive function was
9 assessed using standardized tests of memory, verbal fluency, and speed/concentration. Logistic regression,
10 adjusted for demographic, lifestyle, and health factors, was used to examine the association between PFS
11 and cognitive status. Model performance was evaluated using AUC-ROC and cross-validation.

12 **Results:** PFS exhibited a dose-dependent association with cognitive impairment (adjusted odds ratios: 1.15
13 for moderate, 1.79 for low PFS, compared with higher PFS). PFS demonstrated robust predictive ability for
14 cognition (AUC = 0.75). Sex differences were significant: women with moderate PFS had a 44% higher risk
15 of cognitive impairment (OR: 1.44, 95% CI: 1.15–1.79), while those with low PFS had double the risk (OR:
16 2.28, 95% CI: 1.69–3.08). Associations were weaker in men, even at very low PFS (OR: 1.32, 95% CI:
17 0.91–1.92).

18 **Conclusions:** PFS is a practical tool for predicting cognitive decline, with stronger associations in women.
19 Interventions to improve PF may preserve cognitive health, particularly in older women. Longitudinal
20 studies are needed to confirm these findings.

21 **Key words:** Physical Function Score; Cognitive impairment; Sex-difference; Aging; Prediction model.

1 **Introduction**

2 Cognitive impairment and physical functioning (PF) limitations commonly coexist in aging populations,
3 leading to poorer health outcomes, reduced quality of life, and increased healthcare costs^{1,2}. With increasing
4 global life expectancy, identifying early, modifiable predictors of cognitive impairment is essential³.

5 Growing evidence supports PF as a predictor of cognitive function, highlighting shared pathways such as
6 vascular health, physical activity, and neural integrity^{4,5}.

7 Sex differences in PF and cognition are critical research areas due to higher life expectancy in women⁶ and
8 their disproportionate burden of chronic diseases, PF and cognitive impairments⁷. In low- and middle-
9 income countries^{8,9}, women are more likely to experience physical and cognitive limitations due to
10 biological, social, and cultural factors^{10,11}. However, studies examining sex differences in the associations
11 between PF and cognition remain limited and provide conflicting results¹²⁻¹⁴.

12 Early detection of PF impairments is essential to maintain independence and reduce the risk of cognitive
13 decline⁵. Existing tools for PF assessment, including Berg Balance Scale (BBS)¹⁵, the Short Physical
14 Performance Battery (SPPB)¹⁶ and Timed Up and Go (TUG) test¹⁷ focus on specific domains such as gait
15 speed, balance, or lower extremity strength, and yield mixed results in predicting cognitive decline.. This
16 emphasizes the need for tools that integrate multiple PF aspects to address methodological variations across
17 studies.

18 To address these gaps, this study aimed to develop and validate a Physical Functioning Score (PFS)
19 integrating various components including Activities of Daily Living (ADL), Instrumental ADL (IADL), grip
20 strength, functional limitations, and physical activity into a single tool. Using data from the multinational
21 Health, Alcohol, and Psychosocial factors In Eastern Europe (HAPIEE) cohort, we evaluated PFS as a
22 predictor of cognitive function and explored sex-specific associations. By addressing existing
23 methodological limitations and investigating sex-specific differences, we aimed to enhance understanding of
24 PF as a modifiable risk factor for cognitive decline.

25 **Methods**

26 **Study design and participants**

27 The dataset from the Czech and Polish arms of the multinational HAPEEE project, with a mean participant
28 age of 59 ± 7.3 years old, was used in this study¹⁸. Data on various factors including age, sex, health status,
29 medical examination, lifestyle, socioeconomic and psychosocial factors were collected during 2002-2005
30 (Wave 1). Follow-up surveys were conducted in the Czech Republic and Poland (Wave 2), utilizing face-to-
31 face computer assisted personal interviews combined with clinical examinations. The study included 7,309

1 individuals with complete baseline data (Figure 1).

2 **Measurement of Physical Functioning Score**

3 PFS was calculated from 23 items derived from survey questionnaires and clinical examinations. Scoring
4 variables with over 10 items are recognized as valid predictors of health outcomes¹⁹. Binary variables were
5 coded as using the convention: '0' for the absence of a deficit and '1' for the presence of a deficit. For
6 variables with an intermediate response (e.g., "moderate limit" or "severe limit"), an additional value of '0.5'
7 was assigned. Components included:

8 1. **Activities of Daily Living:**

- 9 • **ADL:** Loss of independence was assessed across six items, including feeding, dressing, bed
10 mobility, toileting, cooking, and shopping.
- 11 • **IADL:** Loss of independence was assessed across four items, including telephoning, taking
12 medications, managing finances, and picking up small objects.

13 2. **Grip Strength:**

14 Grip strength was measured using the Scandidact handgrip dynamometer. Each participant
15 completed two measurements on their dominant hand, and the highest value was used for analysis.
16 Grip strength was categorized into three levels of impairment based on gender-specific cut-off
17 points:

- 18 • **No impairment (0):** Men ≥ 33 kg; Women ≥ 21 kg.
- 19 • **Mild impairment (0.5):** Men 26–33 kg; Women 16–21 kg.
- 20 • **Major impairment (1.0):** Men < 26 kg; Women < 16 kg.

21 3. **Functional limitations:**

22 Ten standardized tests were used to assess health-related limitations in performing various physical
23 activities, such as lifting or carrying grocery bags, climbing stairs (single and multiple flights),
24 bending, kneeling, stooping, and walking distances of 100 meters or 1–2 kilometers. Each limitation
25 was scored as follows:

- 26 • **No limitations:** 3 points
- 27 • **Moderate limitations:** 2 points
- 28 • **Severe limitations:** 1 point

29 A composite score was calculated for each individual, with a maximum of 30 points indicating no
30 limitations. This composite score was categorized into three levels of impairment:

- 31 • **No impairment (0):** Score ≥ 28

- 1 • **Mild impairment (0.5):** Score 25–<28
- 2 • **Major impairment (1.0):** Score < 25

3 4. **Physical Activity:**

4 Physical activity was assessed based on WHO guidelines²⁰as:

- 5 • **Moderate physical activity:** 150 min/week
- 6 • **Vigorous physical activity:** 75 min/week

7 Each type of physical activity was further divided into tertiles, with scores 0, 0.5, and 1.

8 **PFS Calculation and Categorization:**

9 Individual's PFS was calculated by dividing the number of deficits by the total number of items considered.

10 The distribution of PFS by sex is shown in Supplementary Figure 1. To validate the relationship between

11 PFS and cognitive function, the PFS was categorized into five levels based on percentile distribution:

- 12 • **Robust PF:** $PFS \leq 0.03$
- 13 • **Good PF:** $0.03 < PFS \leq 0.07$
- 14 • **Moderate PF:** $0.07 < PFS \leq 0.14$
- 15 • **Low PF:** $0.14 < PFS \leq 0.21$
- 16 • **Very low PF:** $PFS > 0.21$

17 **Outcome**

18 The primary objective was to evaluate the predictive value of PFS in relation to cognitive function.

19 Cognitive function was assessed using four standardized tests adapted from the Consortium to Establish a
20 Registry for Alzheimer's Disease (CERAD). These included:

- 21 1. **Immediate and delayed recall verbal memory:** Assessed using a 10-word learning test.
- 22 2. **Verbal fluency:** Measured by asking participants to name as many animals as possible within one
23 minute.
- 24 3. **Speed and concentration:** Evaluated by asking participants to cross out as many target letters ('P'
25 and 'W') as possible within one minute.

26 All test results were transformed into standardized z-scores, with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1.

27 A composite cognitive function score was then calculated as the average of the z-scores across all tests.

28 The distribution of the composite scores between males and females is shown in Supplementary Figure 2.

29 **Covariates**

30 Covariate data was collected through questionnaires and medical examinations. The variables included were
31 selected based on their established associations with cognitive function and mobility status. Adjustments

1 were made for the following factors:

- 2 • **Demographics:** Age and sex and country.
- 3 • **Socioeconomic Status:** Education level (primary, secondary, college, or university degree),
4 occupation (employed, retired employed, retired unemployed, or unemployed), and deprivation scale
5 (ranging from 1, least deprived, to 12, most deprived).
- 6 • **Lifestyle Factors:** Smoking status (never, current, or past smoker) and alcohol consumption (never,
7 or categorized into frequencies from 1–3 drinks per month to 1–5 drinks per week).
- 8 • **Self-Reported Comorbidities:** Stroke, myocardial infarction, ischemic heart disease, hypertension
9 (defined as measured blood pressure >140/90 mmHg and/or self-reported treated hypertension),
10 diabetes (treated and/or untreated), asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and
11 depression. Depressive symptoms were assessed using the Center for Epidemiologic Studies
12 Depression Scale (CES-D). In the Czech Republic and Poland, a 20-item version was employed. A
13 CES-D score of ≥ 16 (for CES-D 20) was used to classify individuals as having depression²¹.

14 Additional covariates measured during medical examinations included weight and height, which were used
15 to calculate body mass index (BMI), and blood pressure .

16 **Statistical analyses**

17 Descriptive statistics were summarized as means with standard deviations (SD) or frequencies with
18 proportions. To evaluate covariate balance, comparisons were made using standardized differences for PFS,
19 sex, and outcome categories, with differences above 0.10 considered significant. This assessment is
20 presented in Tables 1-2 and Supplementary Table 1.

21 To develop models for PFS, linear, logistic, and quantile regression models were utilized to investigate the
22 relationship between individual PFS components and cognitive impairment. The outcome was assessed as a
23 continuous variable, a binary outcome, and across quartiles of cognitive function (Supplementary Table 2).
24 While linear and logistic regression models assume constant regression coefficients across the population,
25 quantile regression was employed to explore group differences across the full distribution of cognitive
26 function rather than focusing solely on the mean²² (Supplementary Figure 3a).

27 The association between PFS and cognitive impairment was analyzed using unadjusted and adjusted logistic

1 regression models with with the "robust" PFS category serving as the reference group (Supplementary
2 Figure 3b). Odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were estimated for three models: the first
3 was unadjusted, the second adjusted for age, sex, and country, and the third included additional selected
4 predictors.

5 Variables for adjustment were selected based on prior knowledge, available data, and correlations identified
6 in univariate analysis. These variables were further refined using the least absolute shrinkage and selection
7 operator (LASSO) regression^{23,24}, where the optimal lambda value identified the most relevant covariates
8 for adjustment including age, sex, country, occupation, education, alcohol consumption, smoking status,
9 BMI, and comorbidities (Supplementary Tables 3 and 4). Final models were chosen based on the Bayesian
10 Information Criterion (BIC) and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC). BIC
11 accounts for model complexity to optimize fit, while AUC-ROC measures the model's discrimination ability
12 in predicting cognitive impairment as a binary outcome²⁵⁻²⁷ (Supplementary Figure 4). Prediction accuracy
13 was assessed through 10-fold internal cross-validation. The dataset was randomly split into 10 equal subsets.
14 The model was trained on five subsets and validated on the remaining subset, a process repeated until all
15 subsets were used for validation. The cross-validated AUC-ROC was calculated as the average of the AUC-
16 ROC values across all iterations using the `cvauroc` module for cross-validation²⁸ (Supplementary Figure 5).

17 To examine whether men with a given level of PF were more likely to experience cognitive deficits than
18 women, separate stratified analyses were conducted for each PF level in men and women. These results are
19 presented in Table 3.

20 The primary analyses were based on complete case samples. Most of variables had >20% missing data, and
21 participants without missing values were included. Patterns of missing data were analyzed, and multiple
22 imputations (MI) were performed using the Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) method²⁹.
23 Sensitivity analyses were conducted on the imputed dataset to validate the findings, as shown in Table 4.

24 Further sensitivity analyses compared the predictive performance of PFS across quartiles of cognitive
25 function and as a binary outcome (Supplementary Table 2).

26 All statistical analyses were performed using STATA (Version 17, College Station, TX).

27 **Results**

1 **Baseline characteristics of study participants**

2 A total of 7,309 participants had complete data and satisfied the inclusion criteria (Figure 1). This group
3 included 3,427 men (47%) and 3,882 women (53%) (Figure 1). The high proportion of missing data was
4 primarily due to low response rates among Polish participants, as the clinical examination was conducted on
5 a separate day from the initial interview, which led to reduced attendance.

6 Participants with lower PF levels were older, predominantly women, more likely to be retired or
7 unemployed, had lower levels of educational attainment, and higher obesity and comorbidities rates (Table
8 1).

9 Analysis of sex-related differences showed that men had a higher prevalence of smoking and heavy alcohol
10 consumption, and cardiovascular comorbidities with lower cognitive function scores (Table 2). Conversely,
11 women had higher rates of unemployment, socioeconomic deprivation, and comorbidities including asthma
12 and depression (Table 2).

13 Differences in cognitive performance showed that individuals with lower cognitive function were older,
14 predominantly male, and more likely to be retired or unemployed with lower levels of educational
15 attainment and PF and higher level of obesity and comorbidities (Supplementary Table 1).

16 **Association between PF level and cognitive function**

17 The distribution of PFS and cognitive performance by sex is illustrated in Supplementary figures 1 and 2.
18 Women were more frequently represented in groups with low and very low PF, whereas men were at a
19 higher risk of cognitive impairment.

20 PFS demonstrated a significant dose-dependent association with cognitive function. In unadjusted models,
21 ORs ranged from 1.19 (95% CI: 1.04–1.37) for moderate PF to 2.90 (95% CI: 2.38–3.54) for low PF groups
22 (Table 4). After adjustment, the association remained significant but was slightly attenuated, with ORs of
23 1.15 (95% CI: 1.00–1.34) for moderate PF and 1.79 (95% CI: 1.42–2.27) for low PF.

24 **Sex-differences**

25 Sex differences were significant (p for sex heterogeneity = 0.02). Women showed a stronger association
26 between PFS and cognitive function (Table 3). In the fully adjusted model, women with moderate PFS
27 already showed a significant cognitive impairment risk (OR: 1.44, 95% CI: 1.15–1.79), while those with the

1 very low PFS had over doubled the risk (OR: 2.28, 95% CI: 1.69–3.08). In contrast, men with similar PFS
2 levels showed non-significant associations. These findings suggest that the observed relationship between
3 PFS and cognitive function is primarily driven by women, highlighting potential sex-based differences in
4 this association.

5 **Model predictive performance and fit**

6 The predictive discrimination ability of each model was assessed using ROC analysis with 10-fold cross-
7 validation. The AUC for the unadjusted model was 0.58 (95% CI: 0.56–0.59), indicating fair discrimination.
8 The adjusted model demonstrated improved discrimination, with an AUC of 0.75 (95% CI: 0.74–0.77)
9 (Supplementary Figure 4). The average AUC across cross-validation iterations was 0.73, with good
10 calibration agreement between predicted and observed outcomes. (Supplementary Figure 5).

11 Model fit was evaluated using the BIC. The adjusted model (BIC: 8,209) provided a better fit compared to
12 the unadjusted model (BIC: 10,007), suggesting that the inclusion of additional covariates improved the
13 overall performance (Table 4).

14 **Sensitivity analyses**

15 Sensitivity analyses confirmed the robustness of the findings. Results were consistent between complete
16 case analysis and multiple imputation, with no significant differences in the associations or model
17 performance parameters (Table 4). Additionally, cognitive function was analyzed across its full distribution
18 by dividing scores into quartiles. Logistic regression models for these quartiles showed trends consistent
19 with the primary analysis. However, the binary outcome produced more robust results and superior model
20 fit, supporting its use as the primary analytic outcome (Supplementary Table 2).

21 **Discussion**

22 Tthis study found significant associations between composite PFS and cognitive function, with reduced PF
23 linked to poorer cognitive performance in a dose-dependent manner. This relationship remained strong after
24 comprehensive adjustment and was particularly pronounced in women, suggesting potential sex-based
25 differences in the impact of PF on cognitive outcomes. These results underscore the complexity of sex-
26 specific vulnerabilities and their interaction with biological and social factors. PFS showed robust predictive
27 ability and can be used as a practical tool for identifying individuals at risk of cognitive decline in both

1 clinical and research settings.

2 The stronger association observed in women aligns with findings from the Survey of Health, Ageing and
3 Retirement in Europe (SHARE), highlighting the complexity and context-specific nature of sex differences
4 in ageing-related health outcomes. Women across Europe generally experience greater physical limitations
5 compared to men, including higher risk of limitations in ADL and IADL³⁰, increased frailty³¹, and lower
6 grip strength³². Despite these physical limitations, women typically show better cognitive function than men
7 at younger ages (50–59 years), and lower at older ages (80–89 years), particularly in Eastern European
8 regions³². However, our results showing better baseline cognition in women differ from studies in low-
9 income countries where women had significantly lower cognitive function due to limited educational and
10 occupational opportunities^{8,9}. This points to potential physiological and molecular mechanisms, such as
11 higher levels of neurotrophic factors, that may preserve cognitive function in women¹⁴. Conversely, studies
12 from China and Hong Kong reported that moderate-to-vigorous physical activity improved memory and
13 executive function in men, whereas women showed stronger cognitive benefits from light physical
14 activity^{13,33}. While, the recent study exploring the mediated role of social isolation on the pathway of this
15 association did not find any sex differences³⁴. These findings suggest that variations in physical activity
16 patterns and responses between sexes may play a role in the relationship between PF and cognition. In
17 contrast, our results clearly demonstrate sex-based differences, with significantly higher odds of cognitive
18 impairment in women even at moderate PF limitations (OR: 1.44, 95% CI: 1.15–1.79), compared to men.

19 These sex differences suggest underlying variations in biological and social pathways linking PF and
20 cognition. It has been shown that despite the initially greater cognitive reserve women declined faster in the
21 global function³⁵. Hormonal changes, particularly post-menopausal estrogen decline, contribute to
22 musculoskeletal and cognitive changes³⁶. Conditions like osteoporosis and arthritis, more common in
23 women, may contribute to PF impairments^{37,38}. Social factors, including caregiving roles and higher
24 socioeconomic deprivation, may further explain these differences³⁹. In this study, women had lower levels
25 of education and employment that may have contributed to reduced cognitive function, potentially making
26 women more vulnerable to PF-related cognitive decline. Future research should explore these sex-specific
27 pathways to help guide the development of targeted interventions.

28 This study's findings support the evidence that PFS could serve as an early and accessible indicator of
29 cognitive risk. The dose-dependent relationship between PFS and cognitive function aligns with prior

1 findings that greater declines in physical performance measures such as gait speed, balance, or chair rise
2 time are associated with higher rates of cognitive decline and dementia². Faster declines in gait speed have
3 been linked to a twofold higher dementia risk⁴⁰, while poorer balance and chair rise ability predict cognitive
4 decline over time⁴¹. Although some studies, such as the Irish Longitudinal Study on Ageing (TILDA), found
5 no significant association between baseline PF measured with the TUG test and cognitive outcomes,
6 highlighting the need for more comprehensive tools⁴².

7 The composite PFS developed in this study addresses these limitations by integrating multiple PF
8 parameters into a single predictive measure. The inclusion of diverse components in the PFS ensures a
9 comprehensive evaluation of PF. The relationship between each component of this tool and cognitive
10 function is well established. For example, limitations in ADL and IADL, essential indicators of functional
11 independence,^{30,43,44} grip strength, a common measure of muscle function^{32,45} and physical activity⁴⁶ have
12 each been associated with cognitive decline and dementia risk. The strong predictive performance of the
13 PFS (AUC=0.75) highlight its reliability as a clinical tool for identifying cognitive impairment risk,
14 comparable to established clinical assessments.

15 The observed findings align with prior evidence suggesting that PF and cognitive function are
16 interconnected, possibly through shared pathways including vascular health, physical activity, and brain
17 function^{4,5}. Reduced PF may decrease physical activity, social isolation, and diminished engagement in
18 cognitively stimulating activities, leading to cognitive decline⁴⁷. Conversely, cognitive decline, particularly
19 in executive function and visuospatial abilities, associates with poorer motor performance in older adults⁴⁸.

20 Interventions that maintain or improve PF, including structured physical activity or rehabilitation, may help
21 to support cognitive function, especially in older women. From public health perspective, these findings
22 highlight the value of promoting physical function throughout life to preserve cognitive health. Public
23 initiatives could emphasise shared benefits of regular activity for both physical and cognitive wellbeing,
24 while community programs may assist older adults in improving strength, balance, and mobility,
25 contributing to the prevention of cognitive decline at the population level.

26 Strengths of the Study

27 This study has several strengths. First, it is based on a large, multicenter cohort, which enhances the
28 generalizability of the findings. Second, the rigorous development and evaluation of the PFS that align with

best practices for developing health prediction models, such as the TRIPOD guidelines, provides confidence in the score's applicability and generalizability⁴⁹. Third, covariate selection using LASSO regression ensured that only the most relevant predictors were included, enhancing model interpretability and reducing overfitting^{23,24}. The use of ROC-AUC and internal 10-fold cross-validation provided robust measures of predictive performance, while BIC ensured optimal model fit by balancing complexity and accuracy. Fourth, various sensitivity analyses confirmed the robustness of the findings, with consistent results across complete case analyses, multiple imputation, and alternative categorizations of cognitive function.

Limitations of the Study

Despite these strengths, the study has limitations. First, the cross-sectional design of the study prevents any conclusions about temporality and causality. It is unclear whether lower PF leads to cognitive impairment, cognitive decline reduces PF, or both share common underlying mechanisms^{4,5}. Longitudinal studies are needed to clarify the directionality of this relationship. Second, a substantial proportion of participants had missing data, primarily due to low participation rates in clinical examinations among Polish individuals. While multiple imputation was employed to address missing data, selection bias may remain if non-attendance at the clinical examination was driven by unmeasured health factors that also affect cognitive function. In this case, the imputation would not fully account for the bias, potentially affecting the magnitude of the observed associations. Third, the study relied on self-reported and clinician-assessed data, which might be subject to measurement error or reporting bias. Future research should focus on validating the PFS in longitudinal studies and diverse populations to confirm its predictive value over time.

In conclusion, this study supports PFS as a practical predictor of cognitive impairment, especially in women. Its strong performance underscores its potential for identifying those at risk and guiding targeted interventions. Considering PF as a modifiable risk factor may play a critical role in improving cognitive health outcomes in aging populations.

List of abbreviations

HAPIEE: Health, Alcohol and Psychosocial factors in Eastern Europe

PFS: Physical Functioning Score

ADL: Activities of daily living

- 1 **IADL:** Instrumental activities of daily living
- 2 **CERAD:** Consortium to Establish a Registry for Alzheimer's Disease
- 3 **CVD:** Cardiovascular disease
- 4 **COPD:** Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
- 5 **LASSO:** The least absolute shrinkage and selection operator
- 6 **BIC:** Bayesian Information Criterion
- 7 **AUC-ROC:** Area under the receiver operating characteristic curve
- 8 **MICE:** Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations
- 9 **OR:** Odds ratio
- 10 **SD:** standard deviation
- 11 **CI:** confidence interval

12 **Declaration**

13 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

14 All participants provided written informed consent. The study was performed in line with the principles of
15 the Declaration of Helsinki. Approval was granted by the Joint UCL/UCLH Committees on the Ethics of
16 Human Research (Committee Alpha), reference 99/0081; Ethics Committee at the National Institute of
17 Public Health, Prague (reference 2002-01-08/P1) and Bioethics Committee of the Jagiellonian University
18 (reference KE/99/03/B/284).

19 **Data Availability Statement**

20 The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The
21 data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

22 **Competing interests**

23 The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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13 **Authors' contributions**

14 All listed authors contributed to the intellectual conceptualisation of this study. TC, HP and MB codesigned
15 the paper. TC performed the statistical analyses. MB, NC and AP jointly designed the HAPIEE study. TC
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26 **Data statement**

27 The data has not been previously presented orally or by poster at scientific meetings.

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Table 1. Characteristics of the study sample of people according to physical functioning status* (n=7 309)

Variables	High PFS (n=5 020)		Low PFS (n=2 289)		Standardized Difference (Cohen's d)
Age (years), mean SD	57.8	7.0	59.4	7.0	0.2
Age (years), n (%)					0.2
< 50	883	(17.6)	268	(11.7)	
50-59	2 046	(40.8)	888	(38.8)	
60-69	2 016	(40.2)	1 076	(47.0)	
≥ 70	75	(1.5)	57	(2.5)	
Sex, n (%)					0.0
Men	2 376	(47.3)	1 051	(45.9)	
Women	2 644	(52.7)	1 238	(54.1)	
Country, n (%)					0.0
Czech Republic	3 057	(60.9)	1 339	(58.5)	
Poland	1 963	(39.1)	950	(41.5)	
Education, n (%)					0.3
Primary	350	(7.0)	342	(15.0)	
Secondary	1 387	(27.7)	770	(33.8)	
Vocational	2 112	(42.2)	760	(33.3)	
University	1 155	(23.1)	407	(17.9)	
Occupational status, n (%)					0.3
Employed	2 281	(45.7)	726	(31.9)	
Retired/employed	401	(8.0)	177	(7.8)	
Retired/unemployed	2 122	(42.5)	1 285	(56.4)	
Unemployed	189	(3.8)	89	(3.9)	
Smoking status^a, n (%)					0.1
Never	2 351	(47.1)	969	(42.8)	
Past smoker	1 417	(28.4)	681	(30.1)	
Current smoker	1 225	(24.5)	612	(27.1)	
Alcohol consumption^b, n (%)					0.2
Never	796	(16.1)	556	(25.0)	
<1/monthly	1 217	(24.6)	562	(25.2)	
1-3/monthly	1 094	(22.1)	453	(20.4)	
1-4/weekly	1 359	(27.5)	468	(21.0)	
≥5/weekly	477	(9.7)	187	(8.4)	
Deprivation range ^c , mean (SD)	1.5	2.3	2.2	2.8	0.3
BMI categories^d, n (%)					0.3
Normal	1 363	(27.2)	436	(19.0)	
Underweight	7	(0.1)	7	(0.3)	
Overweight	2 349	(46.8)	935	(40.8)	
Obese	1 301	(25.9)	911	(39.8)	
Global cognitive Z-score ^e , mean (SD)	0.09	0.7	-0.17	0.8	0.4
Comorbidities, n (%)					
Hypertension	2 974	(59.3)	1 539	(67.7)	0.2
Myocardial infarction	215	(4.4)	193	(8.8)	0.2
Ischemic heart disease	451	(9.2)	395	(17.9)	0.3
Stroke	82	(1.7)	118	(5.4)	0.2
COPD	476	(9.7)	419	(19.9)	0.3
Asthma	200	(4.1)	176	(8.0)	0.2
Diabetes	454	(9.1)	332	(14.5)	0.2
Depression	873	(17.4)	703	(30.7)	0.3

BMI, body mass index; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

*PF status: Physical functioning score with low PFS category > 50th percentile

^aSmoking category ((current or past heavy smoker (>30 cigarettes per day), moderate smoker (11 - 29 cigarettes per day), or light smoker (<10 cigarettes per day)).

^bAlcohol consumption (never, graduated frequency from 1-3 drinks monthly or 1-5 drinks weekly).

^cDeprivation scale (graded from 1 as a least deprived up to 12 as a most deprived).

^dBMI categories based on WHO recommendations.

^eAge-, sex- and -country specific composite Z-score of all cognitive tests including episodic memory, verbal fluency and mental speed and concentration tests.

Table 2. Characteristics of the study sample of people according to sex (n=7 309)

Variables	Men (n=3 427)		Women (n=3 882)		Standardized Difference (Cohen's d)
Age (years), mean SD	58.7	7.0	57.9	7.0	0.1
Age (years), n (%)					0.1
< 50	485	(14.2)	666	(17.2)	
50-59	1 368	(39.9)	1 566	(40.3)	
60-69	1 494	(43.6)	1 598	(41.2)	
≥ 70	80	(2.3)	83	(1.3)	
Country, n (%)					0.1
<i>Czech Republic</i>	1 991	(58.1)	2 405	(62.0)	
<i>Poland</i>	1 436	(41.9)	1 477	(38.0)	
Education, n (%)					0.4
<i>Primary</i>	173	(5.1)	519	(13.4)	
<i>Secondary</i>	1 209	(35.4)	948	(24.5)	
<i>Vocational</i>	1 159	(34.0)	1 713	(44.3)	
<i>University</i>	872	(25.5)	690	(17.8)	
Occupational status, n (%)					0.2
<i>Employed</i>	1 559	(45.8)	1 448	(37.5)	
<i>Retired/employed</i>	296	(8.7)	282	(7.3)	
<i>Retired/unemployed</i>	1 430	(42.0)	1 977	(51.1)	
<i>Unemployed</i>	119	(3.5)	290	(4.1)	
Smoking status^a, n (%)					0.5
<i>Never</i>	1 154	(34.0)	2 166	(56.1)	
<i>Past smoker</i>	1 278	(37.6)	820	(21.2)	
<i>Current smoker</i>	964	(28.4)	873	(22.6)	
Alcohol consumption^b, n (%)					0.7
<i>Never</i>	378	(11.2)	974	(25.7)	
<i><1/monthly</i>	602	(17.8)	1 177	(31.0)	
<i>1-3/monthly</i>	680	(20.1)	867	(22.9)	
<i>1-4/weekly</i>	1 169	(34.6)	658	(17.3)	
<i>≥5/weekly</i>	547	(16.2)	117	(3.1)	
Deprivation range ^c , mean (SD)	1.4	2.2	2.0	2.6	0.2
BMI categories^d, n (%)					0.3
<i>Normal</i>	689	(20.1)	1 110	(28.6)	
<i>Underweight</i>	2	(0.1)	12	(0.3)	
<i>Overweight</i>	1 741	(50.8)	1 543	(39.7)	
<i>Obese</i>	995	(29.0)	1 217	(31.3)	
Global cognitive Z-score ^e , mean (SD)	-0.14	0.7	0.14	0.7	0.4
PFS related variables					
Physical activity ^f , mean (SD)					
<i>Moderate</i>	11.8	10.4	15.9	12.4	0.4
<i>Vigorous</i>	4.9	5.7	4.9	5.5	0.0
Functional limitations^g, mean (SD)	27.1	3.9	26.2	4.2	0.2
Grip strength, mean (SD), kg	44.6	9.4	27.3	6.3	2.0
Low PFS ^h , n (%)	1 051	(30.7)	1 238	(32.0)	0.0
Comorbidities, n (%)					
<i>Hypertension</i>	2 355	(69.0)	2 158	(55.7)	0.3
<i>Myocardial infarction</i>	299	(8.9)	109	(2.9)	0.3
<i>Ischemic heart disease</i>	431	(12.9)	415	(11.0)	0.1
<i>Stroke</i>	114	(3.4)	86	(2.3)	0.1
<i>COPD</i>	434	(13.0)	461	(12.2)	0.0
<i>Asthma</i>	147	(4.4)	229	(6.1)	0.1
<i>Diabetes</i>	438	(12.8)	348	(9.0)	0.1

<i>Depression</i>	566	(16.5)	1 010	(26.0)	0.2
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BMI, body mass index; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

^aSmoking category ((current or past heavy smoker (>30 cigarettes per day), moderate smoker (11 - 29 cigarettes per day), or light smoker (<10 cigarettes per day)).

^bAlcohol consumption (never, graduated frequency from 1-3 drinks monthly or 1-5 drinks weekly).

^cDeprivation scale (graded from 1 as a least deprived up to 12 as a most deprived).

^dBMI categories based on WHO recommendations.

^eAge-, sex- and -country specific composite Z-score of all cognitive tests including episodic memory, verbal fluency and mental speed and concentration tests.

^fNumber of hours of moderate and vigorous physical activity per week.

^gThe score is based on 10 types of functional limitations, with no limits scored as 3 points, severe limits as 2, and mild limits as 1. A perfect score, with no limitations, is 30 points, and any limitations reduce this maximum score.

^hPF status: PFS with low PF category > 50th percentile

Table 3. Association between level of PFS and risk of cognitive impairment*by sex (n=7 309).

	No. of persons	Male (n= 3 427)			Female (n= 3 882)		
		Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 1 OR (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)
PFS Categories							
<i>Robust</i>	1 829	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PFS</i>	1 690	0.80 (0.66-1.00)	0.83 (0.67-1.00)	0.85 (0.68-1.06)	1.12 (0.93-1.34)	1.15 (0.94-1.40)	1.05 (0.85-1.30)
<i>Moderate PFS</i>	1 501	0.85 (0.69-1.04)	0.89 (0.72-1.09)	0.92 (0.73-1.14)	1.55 (1.28-1.89)	1.55 (1.27-1.89)	1.44 (1.15-1.79)
<i>Low PFS</i>	1 691	1.10 (0.90-1.34)	1.09 (0.89-1.34)	0.96 (0.76-1.20)	2.17 (1.81-2.62)	2.04 (1.68-2.47)	1.57 (1.27-1.95)
<i>Very Low PFS</i>	598	2.25 (1.63-3.11)	2.03 (1.46-2.82)	1.32 (0.91-1.92)	3.88 (3.00-5.02)	3.32 (2.54-4.32)	2.28 (1.69-3.08)
AUC		0.56	0.65	0.73	0.61	0.68	0.75
BIC		4 632	4 467	3 983	5 165	4 957	4 352

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Cognitive function status: Global cognitive Z-score with higher cognitive performance > 50th percentile

[§]Model 1 = unadjusted

Variables selected by LASSO model

[†]Model2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for age, country

[‡]Model 3= Model2 + Adjusted for age, country, occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities.

Table 4. Association between level of PFS and risk of cognitive impairment* (Complete case sample vs imputed sample).

	Complete case (n= 7 309)			Imputed sample (n= 15 560)			
	No. of persons	Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 1 OR (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)
<i>PF Categories</i>							
<i>Robust</i>	1 829	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PFS</i>	1 690	0.98 (0.86-1.12)	0.98 (0.86-1.13)	0.95 (0.82-1.11)	0.98 (0.83-1.14)	0.97 (0.83-1.14)	0.94 (0.79-1.12)
<i>Moderate PFS</i>	1 501	1.19 (1.04-1.37)	1.19(1.03-1.37)	1.15 (1.00-1.34)	1.19 (1.06-1.34)	1.20 (1.04-1.37)	1.11 (0.96-1.29)
<i>Low PFS</i>	1 691	1.59 (1.39-1.82)	1.52 (1.32-1.75)	1.23 (1.06-1.44)	1.58 (1.38-1.80)	1.52 (1.33-1.74)	1.23 (1.07-1.40)
<i>Very Low PFS</i>	598	2.90 (2.38-3.54)	2.66 (2.16-3.27)	1.79 (1.42-2.27)	3.00 (2.43-3.69)	2.69 (2.17-3.34)	1.82 (1.43-2.32)
<i>AUC</i>		0.58	0.69	0.75	0.58	0.69	0.76
<i>BIC</i>		10 007	9 408	8 209	-	-	-

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Cognitive function status: Global cognitive Z-score with higher cognitive performance > 50th percentile

[§]Model 1 = unadjusted

Variables selected by LASSO model

[†]Model2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for age, sex, country

[‡]Model 3= Model2 + Adjusted for age, sex, country, occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities

Figure legends**Figure 1.** Flowchart of exclusion criteria of the HAPIEE study cohort.